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Landscape a Tool for Achievement of Sustainable Development

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ABSTRACT

Landscape open spaces are few and far between as found in many emerging cities of most developing countries and this has served as a deterrent to city development and the achievement of a healthy and sustainable environment. The landscape design is a significant component of effective building design. Landscape elements can provide such benefits to buildings as shielding them from the sun, protecting them against wind, facilitating passive cooling, and providing opportunities for natural ventilation. Furthermore, landscape elements can be useful to clean the air and water, absorb floodwaters, improve aesthetics, provide recreational amenities and develop ecological habitats for wildlife. The poor quality of the city's urban environment has been attributed partly to inadequate use and management of these urban open spaces and this has exerted a major strain on the physical outlook of the environment and an attendant negative effect on the welfare and productivity of the residents. The urbanized world is facing unprecedented social-demographic, technological and environmental changes and in the face of these changes, an important set of questions arises related to how to plan and manage urban green spaces for the benefit of both urban dwellers and biodiversity. The need to effectively address the issue of a sustainable built environment calls for the identification and analyses of the open spaces in a bid to assess their implications to landscape planning and the status of the city's development. This study discusses the concept of sustainability, looking into its principles and the indicators that impact sustainability of the built environment as well as the resultant problems.

Keywords: Landscape, Environmental Sustainability, Landscape irrigation, Landscape elements, Effective Landscaping

1. INTRODUCTION

A landscape is the expression of the interaction between the natural environment and man's activities to make the environment more suitable for his life and needs (Antrop, 2019). Within urban areas, landscapes are highly affected and even dominated by human activities. The outward forms of those city landscapes have significant connections with their economic, social or cultural functions (Wu, Jhjm 2014; Lin et al., 2016).

The environment is an interactive, indispensable medium within and through which man's life routine is carried out. Man's life in his present nature is unimaginable without the environment to supply him with his needs such as air (to breathe), water (to drink and wash with), food (to eat), and solid minerals for fashioning weapons, building shelters and clothing (Atolagbe 2022).

In the last few decades, newer fields integrating natural and social sciences have emerged to investigate urban systems and address complex problems. Urban ecology, an offshoot of ecology, is an

interdisciplinary field that aims to understand the whole city as an ecosystem comprised of both humans and other living organisms that coexist in human dominated systems (Wu, 2014; Gopal et al., 2016).

This exploitation of environmental resources though considered to be inconsequential has evolved with the times and is now evident in uncontrolled urban growth, environmental degradation, deformation and depletion of man's supportive resources and increase in growth, his antagonistic ones. As such, the realisation that its reckless exploitation may spell doom or total annihilation for plants, animals and man alike.

The development of human skills in the use of natural resources to serve human purposes has gradually challenged the natural environment at the local level and then at the global level. However, such challenges did not reach a catastrophic stage until the late 1960s when concern over the deteriorating quality of air, land and forests gave rise to an increased awareness as well as the need to stem pollution and degradation to all components of the environment (Tairu 1998). The resultant situation culminates in what could be called an urban revolution.

In new approach regarding urban ecology, landscape is a visible and noticeable artifact of often unnoticed and sometimes invisible natural and societal processes. Because landscapes are visible, landscape can bring different people into a common experience of environmental systems. Across all scales of environmental phenomena, the scale at which landscape patterns are perceived by humans, the "perceptible realm," is decisive for landscape change (Gobster et. al, 2007; Nassauer, 2012).

The results of this urban revolution—congestion, crowding and pollution—are destroying the natural environment and eroding the quality of life for millions of human beings. Of the six billion people on earth, about one billion live in squalid slums that surround burgeoning cities in the developing world. In spite of these serious problems, experts predict that urban areas will continue to expand, and that in 20–30 years nine of the ten largest "mega cities" (with populations over 10 million) will be in the developing world, where public services are already strained beyond capacity. (Fadamiro 2006)

3. METHODOLOGY

In this research, in order to gain necessary information and data, methods like observation, quantitative survey, qualitative survey and data analysis were used. These methods have been useful to collect and search both primary and secondary data of the research. The observation was conducted as a pilot survey on selected parks to gain the information how urban dweller interacts with nature in urban parks. After these observations, preparation of the survey involved the development of a questionnaire for the quantitative and qualitative survey of data. The survey included the visitors of both gardens. This qualitative survey was conducted in a face-to-face manner which was very important for getting instant feedback from the participants. From the qualitative survey also we could identify the problem which was not obvious through the observation. The quantitative survey involved the users and visitors of both gardens.

2. LANDSCAPE CONCEPTS

Before discussing landscape design techniques, some general comments about plants are important. The selection of proper plant material requires knowledge of concepts such as growth habits, origin, species` adaptations, and plant biological processes. It is also important to have a comprehension of contextual topics, including local and global hydrologic systems, precipitation, seasonal temperature fluctuations, wind, and geography. Some of the critical concepts and topics necessary for understanding landscape design as it relates to proper building design are discussed as follows (Car penter & Walker, 1998; Marsh, 2010; Vassigh at all, 2013).

Landscape plants are herbaceous plants and woody plants. Herbaceous plants do not produce woody stems and are known botanically as herbs. They may have an upright, prostrate, or viney growth habit. Woody plants can be classified as trees, shrubs, or woody vines. The distinction between trees and shrubs is not always apparent. Generally, trees are characterized by a single upright stem or trunk, whereas shrubs have several stems. In addition, trees usually are taller than shrubs. The distinctions, however, may be obscured by pruning, training, or environmental conditions.

Among woody plants, a major distinction is made between deciduous plants, and evergreen plants. Evergreen plants are classified as either broadleaved evergreens or needle evergreens. Conifers constitute the needle evergreen group. Plants may also be classified on the basis their life span. Annual plants complete their life cycles in one growing season and must be planted anew each year. Biennial plants complete their life cycles in two growing seasons. Perennial plants grow year after year. Annuals and biennials are only herbaceous; perennials can be either herbaceous or woody. Some woody perennials are not totally hard in cold climates and act like herbaceous perennials. There are a variety of characteristics by which to describe or classify plants and distinguish them from one another. Among these, growth habit, seasonal persistence, and ecological origin are particularly important with regard to sustainability.

Importance of Landscape

Worldwide adoption of landscaping can assist in developing a sustainable built environment, this however is yet to gain a good foothold in Nigeria as in many other third world countries. Places associated with landscaping in Nigeria are churches, educational institutions (nursery, primary schools, secondary and tertiary institutions of higher learning), sport complexes, squares, residential quarters, major roads and highways, parks, hospitals, industrial neighbourhoods, e. t. c., their major utility is for aesthetics, comfort and convenience.

The importance of landscape include the following:

a. Effects on locations: Landscaping improves the urban climate by providing shades along streets in hot regions. They can be open spaces with shades and lower temperatures in hot cities. They provide protection from cold winds in temperate climates.

b. Effects on the ecology: Landscaping reduces the impact of noise generated by traffic, neighbours and children at play, e. t. c. within and around residential areas. They act as agents that could retain and absorb rainwater, act as flood control and help protect natural flora and fauna. They are also beneficial in reducing air pollution from vehicles, manufacturing, heating installations and natural dust.

c. Socio-Psychological Effects: By providing spaces for play, children of different ages can interact. Other areas if earmarked for recreation among youths, adults and elderly persons

Factors Affecting Effective Landscaping

The limitless exploitation of man's living environment by the conscious and unconscious activities carried out to satisfy his needs leads to factors that affect the landscape. A reflection of this is seen in the

environmental degradation, deformation and depletion of the earth's resources; all of which spell doom to man and his immediate environment if the necessary checks and balances against these factors are not put into place in good time. Some of these factors as identified from the study include:

- 1. Factors: Climatic and Environmental** As an important consideration in landscape design, nature involves the world of forces and processes in which we live and work; as such, man and all his activities are an inextricable part of it. Fairbrother (1974) stated that while users requirements are the starting point of any landscape design, the physical arrangement of the landscape materials should be undertaken as a creative exercise which evolved in the first place from a consideration of the interacting complex of climate, geology, vegetation, wildlife and all other elements in the natural scene.
- 2. Lack of Topographical Maps:** This map is essential for any meaningful landscape site analysis by showing the contour structure, shape of the land, ground forms and other physical properties. These topographical maps when analysed give site scenery patterns, slope access and communication
- 3. Site Factor:** Site planning provides the introduction of functional elements that will serve against wind, noise and help screen undesirable views into or out from the site. They give privacy as visual link to frame views or form focal points, to outline shades and create space division within the context of any functional planning.
- 4. Cost:** This is an important consideration particularly in the rural settings where poverty has eaten deep into the economic fabric thus leading to other psychological effects.
- 5. Maintenance:** To achieve the purpose of landscaping, a good maintenance programme or attitude is essential; else the maturity in the form envisaged would not materialise. The maintenance schedule should accompany the site plan.
- 6. Use Factor:** These can be considered as a part of the basis for any meaningful site design and planning. They include primary function of the site, subsidiary functions or multiple uses, density of use, access and traffic requirements, the appearance of the landscape both within and beyond the site to mention a few.

4. LANDSCAPE IRRIGATION

Water is an essential life element. Employing proper landscape design strategies plays a significant role in conserving water and reducing the demand on potable water supplies. The use of low-irrigation plant materials, efficient irrigation systems, and the expanded use of treated wastewater or harvested rainwater for irrigation can help to achieve significant reductions in water use.

- 5. Landscaping Well-designed landscaping can make a significant difference in the amount of energy required to maintain a comfortable building. Proper use of trees, shrubs, vines and man-made structures can modify the climate around a building to reduce heat gains in summer and heat losses in winter. Plants can protect a building from winter winds and shade it from summer sun. In fact, heat exchange in a building occurs through three major processes as air infiltration, heat conduction and transmission of solar radiation (Walker & Newman, 2009).**

The first heat exchange process in air infiltration is the passage of outside air through cracks around windows and doors or other openings in building walls or ceilings. Air pressure on surfaces that face the wind are subject to increased air pressure as wind velocity increases. Air enters the building through openings in these surfaces. In winter, heat losses due to air infiltration may represent up to half of the total heat losses on the windiest, coldest days. Properly placed plants can reduce air infiltration by reducing wind velocity near the building.

The second heat exchange process is heat conduction through materials from which the building is built. The amount of heat conduction depends on the insulating property of the building materials, thickness of materials, and the temperature difference between the inner and outer surfaces of the building. Landscaping can help control the temperature difference between the inner and outer surfaces of walls and ceilings, and thus reduce heat conduction. The outer surface temperature is controlled mainly by outside air temperature, wind velocity and solar radiation. In summer, trees and shrubs can reduce the

amount of solar radiation reaching the outside surfaces of a building, and thus reduce heat conduction into the building. In the winter, solar heating can reduce the rate of heat loss by raising the outside temperature of walls. Blocking cold winter winds also reduces conductive heat loss. The third process for heat exchange in a building is transmission of solar radiation through windows. Large expanses of east or west-facing glass admit undesirable solar radiation in the summer. Large expanses of south-facing glass can help heat a building in winter. Vegetation around a building can regulate solar radiation during different seasons of the year. In fact, solar radiation has significant impact on building. The extent of this impact is dependent upon several factors, including building orientation, architectural form, materiality and landscape. The heating, cooling, and lighting of a building are very much affected by the site and landscape in which the building is located. Plants are immensely useful in the heating, cooling, and lighting of buildings. Through the proper location and selection of plants, well-designed landscaping can greatly reduce energy consumption of a building. Plants promote heating primarily by reducing infiltration and partly by creating air spaces next to buildings, which act as extra insulation. Shading of a building's surfaces during periods of the most intense solar radiation, particularly in hot climates and seasons, can be highly effective in reducing excessive thermal heat loads on the building. The shade from tree is better than the shade from a man-made canopy because the tree does not heat up and reradiate down. This is the case because of the multiple layers that are ventilated and because the leaves stay cool by the transpiration of water from the leaves. Transpiration cools not only the plant but also the air in contact with the vegetation. Thus, the cooling load on a building surrounded by trees or grass will be smaller than on a building surrounded by asphalt or concrete. Trees are more effective than grass in providing comfort. Usually the best plants to use are native varieties that have adapted to the local climate, soil and pathogens. Thus, less water, fertilizer, and chemicals are needed for healthy plant growth. At night, trees work against natural cooling by blocking long-wave radiation. There will be more radiant cooling in an open field than under a canopy of trees.

Plants can also improve the quality of daylight entering through windows. Direct sunlight can be scattered and reduced in intensity, while the glare from the bright sky can be moderated by plants. Vines across the windows or trees farther away can have the same beneficial effect.

In recent years, vegetated green roofs have become very popular, but for reducing the cooling load on a building, vegetated green walls are often more effective. Plants are most helpful on the east and west walls, which are exposed mostly to the summer sun. The north wall needs the least shading, and the south wall's shading needs depend on the building type and climate. The plants can also help shade the east and west windows. Shading south windows with plants on buildings that need winter heat is a challenge because even deciduous plants shade a great deal.

On the other hand, the proper choice and positioning of plants can greatly improve the microclimate of a site. The selection of these plants is very important. In this connection, advice should be obtained from such sources as local nurseries, foresters, agriculturists and landscape architects.

5. Landscaping elements

Simple strategies utilizing landscape planting elements such as trees, shrubs, groundcovers or vines in key locations and in proper quantities can greatly reduce energy consumption. Appropriately utilized landscape elements and systems can deflect and diffuse sunlight or dissipate solar heat energy to moderate thermal loads and reduce requirements for mechanical cooling (Walker, 1991: Haque, et al., 2004: Kachadorian, 1997).

6. SUSTAINABLE ENVIRONMENTS

The sustainability of the intrinsic environment promotes less depletion of natural resources, pollution and consumption of energy. When this done, a gradual reduction of the green house gases comes into play. Some countries with successful green building programs, architects, engineers, and builders are employing largely existing methods and simulation tools as well as offtheshelf technologies to create and build facilities with lower environmental impact, reduced resource consumption, and significantly improved interior environments.

Benefits of sustainable landscaping

- i. Contribution to mental health as a result of restorative effects of nature.
- ii. Contribution to physical health through utilisation of recreation parks, open spaces and playing fields designed and maintained in a sustainable manner.
- iii. Environmental benefits through bio climatic influence of trees and plant materials leading to lower temperatures and increased emission of oxygen.
- iv. Economic benefits through emergent job opportunities, tourism and a resultant improved property values.
- v. Social benefits resulting from community participation in developmental programmes.
- vi. Landscaping is one of the most cost effective tools for improving and sustaining the quality of life and the living environments: be it in the city or in the rural areas. Although impeding factors such as climatic conditions, funds, and ignorance among others as identified above exist, landscaping should be embraced and inculcated in the general master plan and design of a community. The success of landscape improvement rests on the level of commitment of the community's involvement in development programmes of this nature and as such must not be overlooked.

CONCLUSION

The architectural design and landscaping have a tremendous effect on the heating, cooling and lighting of a building. In that case, buildings can be combined into landscaping techniques. These techniques can reduce a building's energy requirements during all four seasons, by blocking out the hot summer sun, encouraging warming solar radiation in winter, deflecting cold winter winds and channeling breezes for cooling in spring, summer and fall. In reducing the amount of cooling energy required by a building, landscaping may be useful by directly shading the building with trees, shrubs or vines, shading the area around the building to lower the temperature of its surroundings, and using ground covers to reduce sunlight reflected into the building and lower the surrounding ground temperatures.

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Landscaping can also benefit a building in winter by decreasing infiltration. Since higher wind speeds mean higher infiltration rates, planting windbreaks to reduce the wind speeds approaching the building can lower its energy needs. Locate the windbreak on the windward side of the building in a way that it does not interfere with solar access. Use evergreen trees and shrubs for windbreaks on the windward side. If sunlight or a view is important, a combination of deciduous trees and shrubs may be used, but this will be less effective.

The windbreak should be dense, rather than solid, because solid wind breaks create turbulence behind them. The density of the windbreak should be maintained from the ground up with out major gaps. A mixture of various shrubs and trees can help prevent these gaps. It is also a good idea to mix species within the windbreak to avoid the possibility of losing the entire wind break to a disease which affects one species.

Landscaping may also be used to help cool a building by leaving an open Channel between trees or hedges in the direction of summer winds to direct the breezes on and into the building. Unfortunately, channeling summer breezes for cooling is worthwhile only if the building's personal tends to use natural cooling practices.

In short, in a strategic landscaping:

- Shade the east and west faces of the building, giving top priority to the west side, and giving priority to shading windows over shading walls.
- Avoid shading of surfaces to be used for solar collection.
- Shade the area surrounding the building.
- Cover bare ground with lawns or other ground covers rather than paving where possible.

- Plant to provide a channel for summer breezes, if natural ventilation is used, and if it doesn't conflict with planting for a windbreak.

On the other hand, vegetated surface systems such as green roof, vine-covered wall and living wall are built on the façades and roofs of buildings to protect from solar heat in several ways. These systems can potentially offer an additional insulating layer to a building, helping to maintain the temperatures inside, and providing the effective environmental impact outside.

In addition to, well-designed landscaping has a significant role in conserving irrigation water. In this connection, the use of low-irrigation plant materials and efficient irrigation systems can help to achieve significant reductions in water use.

REFERENCES

- Atolagbe, A.M.O. (2002): Architecture in Nigeria and the practice for sustainable Development: A comparative study of Modern And Indigenous Housing Strategy". AARCHES Journal, Vol. 2, No 1, Oct 2001Nov. 2002.pp 6165.
- Antrop, M., (1998). Landscape change: plan or chaos?. *Landscape and Urban Planning*, 41,155–161.
- Badri Benam, N. & Moosavi, M.S. (2012). An architectural approach to characterization of modern healthcare environments, *J. Appl. Environ. Biol. Sci.*, 2(9)460-465.
- Bainbridg, D.A., & Haggard, K. (2011). *Passive solar architecture: heating, cooling, ventilation, daylighting and more using natural flows*. Vermont: Chelsea Green Publishing Company.
- Bertauski, T. (2009). *Designing the landscape: An introductory guide for the landscape designer*. New Jersey: Pearson Prentice Hall.
- Carpenter, P.L., & Walker, T.D. (1998). *Plants in the landscape*. Illinois: Waveland Press, Inc.
- Dunnett, N., & Kingsbury, N. (2008). *Planting green roofs and living walls*. London: Timber Press.
- Gopal, S., Tang, X., Phillips, N., Nomack, M., Pasquarella, V., & Pitts, J., (2016). Characterizing urban landscapes using fuzzy sets. *Computers, Environment and Urban Systems*, 57 (2016) 212–223.
- Gobster, P. H., Nassauer, J. I., Daniel, T. C., & Fry, G., (2007). The shared landscape: What does aesthetics have to do with ecology?. *Landscape Ecology*, 22, 959–972.
- Golzarian, M., & Zarei, S., (2013). An analysis to role of gardens as urban space in historic structure of Tabriz. *Journal of Basic and Applied Scientific Research*, 3(6): 87-91.
- Hami, A., Suhardi Bin, M., Manohar, M., & Shahhosseini, H., (2011). Users' preferences of usability and sustainability of old urban park in Tabriz. *Iran. Australian Journal of Basic and Applied Sciences*. 5 (11): 1899-1905.
- Haque M.T., Tai, L., & Ham, D. (2004). "Landscape design for energy efficiency". USA: Carolina Energy Office, Clemson University Digital Press.
- Kachadorian, J. (1997). *The passive solar house: using solar design to heat & cool your home*. Second edition. Vermont: Chelsea Green Publishing Company.
- Lechner, N. (2015). *Heating, cooling, lighting: sustainable design methods for architects*. Fourth edition. New Jersey: John Wiley & Sons, Inc.
- Lelhaj, R. & Moosavi, M.S. (2014). Considering the effect of gender on women's understanding of architectural spaces, *European Online Journal of Natural and Social Sciences*, 3 (4), 520-533. Openly accessible at <http://www.european-science.com>.
- Lin, T., Sun, C., Li, X., Zhao, Q., Zhang, G., Ge, R., Ye, H., Huang, N., & Yin, K., (2016). Spatial pattern of urban functional landscapes along an urban–rural gradient: A case study in Xiamen City, China. *International Journal of Applied Earth Observation and Geoinformation*, 46 (2016) 22–30.
- Marsh, W.M. (2010). *Landscape planning environmental applications*. Fifth edition. New York: John Wiley & Sons, Inc.
- Melby, P. (1995). *Simplified irrigation design*. Second edition. New York: John Wiley & Sons, Inc.
- Seçkin, Ö.B. (2003). *Peyzaj uygulama tekniği*. İstanbul: İ.Ü. Basım ve Yayınevi
- Nassauer, J., (2012). Landscape as medium and method for synthesis in urban ecological design. *Landscape and Urban Planning*, 106 (2012) 221– 229.

- Press, London. 1970. Spreiregen P. D. (1965): *Urban Design: The Architecture of Towns and Cities*. McGraw Hill Book Company, London.
- Ragozino, S., (2016). Tools for regeneration of the urban landscape social enterprise as a link between people and landscape. *Procedia- Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 216 (2016)201– 208
- Tairu, T.T. (1998), *Towards Protection of Environment and Ecology*. Current Issues in Nigerian Environment. Ed. Prof. A. Osuntokun, Davidson Press, Ibadan.
- Wu, J., (2006). Landscape ecology, cross-disciplinarity, and sustainability science. *Landscape Ecology*, 21, 1–4.
- Wu, J., (2010). Landscape of culture and culture of landscape: does landscape ecology need culture? *Landscape Ecology*, 25, 1147–1150.
- Wu, J., (2014). Urban ecology and sustainability: the state-of-the-science and future directions. *Landscape and Urban Planning*, 125, 209–221.
- Zahedian, E. & Moosavi, M.S. (2013). A morphological approach to characterization of urban space in historical structure of cities in Iran, *J. Appl. Environ. Biol. Sci.*, 3(10) 59-66.